

FORENSICITY AND DIALECTISM IN CHIMAMANDA NGOZI ADICHIE'S *AMERICANAH*

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Abstract

One of the ways Chimamanda Adichie's third novel, *Americanah* (2013) reflects reality is through its consistent references, inquiries, and inclusions of diverse significant contemporary and historical developments in society. Applying New Historicism as a theoretical parameter, the study unveils that the author utilizes the instrumentality of her novelistic enterprise as a veritable tool for forensic inquiry into certain past thorny societal issues which till date continue to generate public concern, debate and even controversies. It is in this context that some spectacular insights the fiction offers concerning some questionable involvements of certain military regimes and governments in Nigeria are quite revealing and thought provoking. The researcher also observes some insightful representations of certain admirable and adorable sides of history which all the more contribute in making the fiction realistic and vivid, thus aiding in connecting and reconnecting an informed reader to various memorable historical resources. These amply portray that Adichie possesses a deep understanding of society's sociopolitical and historical experiences and has represented them in her novel in the process of discharging her artistic burdens. The study avers that such representations of the past in a fictional work, apart from enabling to make the work realistic, also serves as reminders of history and would equally enable citizens in contemporary times to ascertain whether or not society is really making any meaningful progress politically, socially, economically and otherwise. The study, therefore, significantly demonstrates that to understand and appropriately interpret the present conditions of society, a grounded knowledge of the past is necessary, and that literature can, among other things, function as a vital investigative instrument.

Key words: Forensic, Dialectism, Society, Representation, Interpretation

INTRODUCTION

Literature is often traditionally assigned the educative and entertainment functions. These functions, particularly that of entertainment sometimes portray the demanding task of literary analysis and studies as being less serious or valuable to society than studies in other related disciplines such as Law, Political Science, Sociology and Anthropology, etc. Yet Literature being a mirror of society can also serve as a veritable tool, avenue, even arsenal to investigate and argue both historical and contemporary issues which it often mirrors in one form or the other in society. So the lexical items “forensicity” and “dialectism” as derivatives of the root words “forensic” and “dialectics” are applied in the study in the context and implications of “investigation” and logical “argumentation.” Of course, the danger of a one-sided presentation and interpretation of developments in society can be enormous. Its consequences can be compared to that of what Adichie (2009) refers to as the “the danger of a single story.” In that celebrated speech delivered on October 7 at the TED conference, she warns that if only a single story is told and heard about another person and country, we risk a critical misunderstanding. But when there are diverse presentations and representations on any societal issue, one can be in a better position to strike a balance and to arrive at a reliable conclusion which can contribute in bringing the desired societal transformation, indict the guilty and vindicate the innocent. Adichie maintains that “stories have been used to dispossess and and to malign. But stories can also be used to empower and to humanize. Stories can break the dignity of a people. But stories can also repair that broken dignity... when we reject the single story, when we realize that there is never a single story about any place, we regain a kind of paradise.” These assertions can be said to be equally relevant to issues relating to historical presentations and interpretations in the discipline of history and in literary studies. In both cases, materials are usually drawn from developments in society. Needless to say that one of the ways of making a fictional work to be realistic, concrete and aesthetically endearing, as opposed to fantasy, is by creatively invoking actual memorable contemporary and historical developments in society through allusions, character mimesis and various kinds of intertextual representations and conformations. It is with respect to this that Duhan (2015, p.192-197) asserts that,

A literary man is as much a product of his society as his art is a product of his own reaction to life. Even the greatest of artists is sometimes a conscious, sometimes an unconscious exponent of his time-spirit. The time-spirit is the total outcome, the quintessential accretion of all the political, social, religious and scientific changes of a particular age. The historical aspect of literature...cannot be ignored. Thus literature reflects his zeitgeist or the Time-Spirit... No writer can escape the influence of his age. Every man is... the citizen of his age as well as of his country... One belongs to one's century and race, even when one reacts against one's century and race. Thus literature always expresses the thoughts and sentiment of human mind which are closely connected with and conditioned by the age. The influence of the age on the human mind is due to the fact that the latter is constantly influenced by the spirit of the age and reacts to it vividly and vigorously... We all know that literature mirrors society. What happens in a society is reflected in literary works in one form or the other.

The society being mirrored or reflected in a work of literature in any form, as earlier stated, can be either contemporary or historical. This study is particularly concerned with how Chimamanda Adichie has mirrored society in *Americanah*, using the instrumentality of her fiction to investigate and interrogate certain developments as well as dialectise. Such forms of dialectisation or argumentation on some of such well known societal issues have indeed added fresh insights even if imaginary. Again, if the metaphor of a mirror will still be employed and possibly extended, a number of questions will be earnestly begging for answers. How does one make use of a mirror? What factors can prompt one to go for a mirror in order to make use of it? What is the purpose of going for a mirror after being prompted by any particular factor? Then after going for a mirror, does any form of decision, appraisal or resolution come to mind at all? In pondering over these critical questions, Dunhan's (2015, p.192, 194) assertions, again, come to mind:

Literature indeed reflects the society, its good values and its ills. In its corrective function, literature mirrors the ills of the society with a view to making the society realize its mistakes and make amends. It also projects the virtues or good values in the society for people to emulate. Literature as an imitation of human action often presents a picture of what people think, say and

do in the society. In literature, we find stories designed to portray human life and action through some characters who, by their words, action and reaction, convey certain messages for the purpose of education, information and entertainment. It is impossible to find a work of literature that excludes the society, since no writer has been brought up completely unexposed to the world around him. What writers of literature do is to transport the real-life events in their society into fiction and present it to the society as a mirror with which people can look at themselves and make amends where necessary. Thus literature is not only a reflection of the society but also serves as a corrective mirror in which members of the society can look at themselves and find the need for positive change. It is, thus, clear that if we are interested in literature, its influence is bound to move us amply.

Dunhan's perception of the multidimensional functions of a work of literature is in conformity with that of Arisky (2019) who also views literature as a powerful tool for societal transformation when he avers that literary art is the result of social action and in turn gives rise to social action. The literary text, then, can therefore always be affirmed to be an integral and inseparable part of a much larger cultural, political and social discourse. Not unconnected to the historical moment of its creation, the literary text is directly involved in history and can be utilized to investigate history.

Theoretical Framework

Literary research or criticism can be compared to a building construction project which often uses the plumbline, in this case theoretical framework, to ascertain the alignment of the structure. According to *Wikipedia* (2020), the major use of the plumbline in a building project is to "ensure that constructions are 'plum' or vertical" ("Plumbline"). As a vertical reference line instrument, the builder's plumbline indispensably enables him to determine the vertical from any given point at each stage of the construction work. In the same vein, a theoretical framework serves as a veritable guide to a literary researcher or critic and enables him to maintain a steady orientation in his evaluation of a work of literature so as to produce meaningful results, and also restrains him from straying to extraneous trajectories. It is in view of the essential role theoretical framework plays in literary research that Nwahunanya (2012, p.1-5) states:

A theory of literature is therefore sine qua non for a proper appreciation of literature. A sound critical theory is the basic foundation upon which any critical procedure must stand, and from there emerge. From critical theory we get the basic assumptions for the study of literature and we gain an insight into literary categories, using generalizable principles. The literary theorist re-examines the fundamental assumptions behind the critical evaluation of any tradition of literature with the aim of correcting them if they are faulty, setting up proper criteria, and thereby aiding readers in the correct interpretation of literary texts. Through analytic descriptions, critical theory anatomizes the essential nature of literary artifacts and isolates their components. ...From all the above, it ought to be clear that critical theory is the basis of all literary criticism.

Before Nwahunanya's insightful submissions on critical theory as stated above, Culler (2007, p.1) had noted that it involves "the systematic study of the nature of literature and of the methods used in the practical reading of literature. By literary theory, we refer not to the meaning of a work of literature but to the theories that reveal what literature can mean." Nwaru (2014, p. 21) concurs to these when she asserts that,

Theoretical systems are constructs which allow the critic to investigate aspects of literature, and to pass along those insights that are yielded up. Literature, being a cultural product, is localizable in time and space. As a result, modern analysts classify literary works according to their critical orientations, that is according to where the critic locates the literary work.

The critical theory applied to this research as earlier stated is New Historicism. It is a theory which evolved in the 1980s largely through the work of the American scholar and critic, Stephen

Greenblatt and really gained a global influence in the 1990s. New Historicism claims to be a more neutral approach to historical occurrences, and to be sensitive in assessing diverse cultures. It is an approach largely influenced by structuralist and post-structuralist theories and strives to reconnect a work of art with the historical period in which it was produced as well as linking it with the cultural and political movements of the era. A major assumption of the theory is that every work of art is an output or product of the historic time or moment that created it. Another prominent New Historicist - the French philosophical historian Michel Foucault based his approach both on the theory of the limits of collective cultural knowledge and on his technique of evaluating a large array of documents in order to comprehend the episteme of a particular time. In consonance with Foucault's perception and method, New Historicists believe that literary studies and their relationship to history have been very narrow and therefore needs to be widened. This brings about the notion that 'history' is textual. Steven Lynn (1994, P.120) elaborates this when he states that "...the new historicist assumes that history is a story, a construct necessarily written and re-written." This is to say that New Historicists believe that it is impossible for history to be written without ideological and institutional analysis which includes the evaluation of the act of writing itself. This, according to Hutcheon (1998) inevitably implicates the historian, the theorist and the critic in both ideologies and institutions. Bressler (1999, p.238) who refers to the theory as "cultural poetics" states that New Historicism,

...declares that all history is subjective, written by people whose personal biases affect their interpretation of the past. History, asserts cultural poetics, can never provide us with truth or give us a totally accurate picture of past events or the worldview of a group of people. Disavowing the old historicism's autonomous view of history, cultural poetics declares that history is one of many discourses or ways of seeing or thinking about the world. By highlighting and viewing history as one of many equally important discourses such as sociology and politics, and by closely examining how all discourses (including that of textual analysis itself) affect a text's interpretation, cultural poetics or New Historicism claims to provide its adherents with a practice of literary analysis that highlights the inter-relatedness of all human activities and admits its own prejudices. In New Historicism, literary and non-literary texts are not ranked but are analysed on equal significance with each other, all influencing all other texts; a development in reaction and in dialogue with formalism.

New Historicism is considered to be appropriate and suitable for this research because it gives room for an unfettered and panoramic historical interpretations of a literary text which in-turn ensures a yielding of a broad array of meanings from which society can possibly draw veritable lessons for growth, peaceful co-existence and sustainable development.

ISSUES AND DISCUSSIONS

Adichie's investigations, representations and utilization of societal historical developments in *Americanah* is transnational. One of the dominant historical representations we meet in the novel is that of a landmark historical occurrence in the United States of America; the historic nomination of the first black man, Barack Obama, as the presidential candidate of the Democrats and his subsequent election to the White House as the President of the world's most powerful nation in November 2008. Obama's presidency was inaugurated on 20th January 2009 amidst loud global jubilation, particularly among people from the black race. The various stages of Obama's emergence and eventual electoral victory are elaborately infused in the novel to spice up the story at different points and in different ways. In Nigeria, a number of significant historical developments beginning from the administration of Alhaji Shehu Shagari in the late seventies and early eighties, to that of Major General Muhammadu Buhari who ousted the Shagari administration to Generals Babangida and Abacha, and then to the civilian-elected administration of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo are insightfully foregrounded and

interrogated from the perspectives of various characters in the novel. Just as in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Adichie almost follows the path of historical accuracy in foregrounding and discussing some historical events in those administrations by using the real names of those national leaders before making vivid references to some conspicuous historical developments under their leaderships. Adichie is also preoccupied with issues bordering on emigration, love, race and identify politics. Again, as in her debut, *Purple Hibiscus*, military dictatorship forms a significant background to this third novel. It is on account of military dictatorship and a disorderly society and economy created by it that people start to flee from the country if they can afford the means. Ifemelu's emigration to America and Obinze's precarious existence in his undocumented stay in London are all prompted by the harsh socioeconomic realities of their own nation as orchestrated by high-wire politicking and military dictatorship. It is in view of this that Nwanyanwu (2017, p. 2-3) observes that,

The post-independence period in Nigeria during the 1980s and 1990s has been marked by massive economic and academic emigration to the stable and prosperous West (notably the United States of America and the UK) ...Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's third novel *Americanah* takes us into the sojourns of her female protagonist Ifemelu and other Nigerian youngsters who try to escape the choicelessness of the Nigerian society in the 1980s.

By subscribing to the expression "...massive... academic emigration..." Nwanyanwu concurs to the name tag "brain drain," which is often used to refer to that period in Nigeria's chequered political history. The tag denotes the mass emigration of capable and seasoned Nigerian intellectuals to other nations of the world where they considered safe and better; where they sought for the much spoken greener pasture. Adichie's consistent reflection and portrayal of such issues in the history of the country prompts Akingbe and Adeniji (2017, p.37) to refer to her as "... a burgeoning Nigerian writer who continually forges the link between Nigeria's past and present." It can be recalled that in *Purple Hibiscus*, Auntie Ifeoma – a seasoned academic at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka also takes similar decision as Ifemelu and Obinze in *Americanah* as a result of the suffocating military dictatorship the country is experiencing. Adichie demonstrates that without dictatorship as a factor, and the unstable socioeconomic condition it orchestrated in the entire nation, there would probably have been no other cogent reason for Ifemelu's and Obinze's hasty and desperate emigration to US and UK respectively. It is on account of this thematic preoccupation of emigration, race and transculturalism that Adichie's exploration of historical resources traverses three continents – Africa, Europe and America. It is from this perspective that Espirito (2008, p.4) notes that "...Adichie expands the range of representation of African subjects through the complexity of her main characters and the cultural tensions they must confront at home and abroad." Again, it is also on account of such "expansion" that Adichie makes the reader to witness racial politics in Europe and America, particularly in America.

On the blurb of *Americanah*, Binyavanga Wainaina has maintained that the novel is "...powerful and the most political of Chimamanda's novels." Of course power, politics and history have often moved together as companions, such that to discuss any of them in isolation is almost impossible. A meaningful political discourse or even debate at any point in time does not usually go far without a portrayal of either the use or abuse of power and reference to things that preceded the present (history). As earlier stated, one of the most detailed historical issues Adichie uses the instrumentality of her artistic creation in *Americanah* to investigate and interrogate are the issues surrounding the presidential candidacy of Barack Obama. Here it must be stated that unlike *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun* where the author is a bit conservative in the use of names of actual historical figures, she is bolder, even daring in *Americanah* in that she calls most of her fictionalized historical characters by their real names (sometimes in full) and characterises them in conformity with some actual historical developments surrounding their lives. This sort of boldness as demonstrated by Adichie in *Americanah*

is a major feature of third generation Nigerian writing where her works are usually categorized. Unlike the first and second generations of Nigerian writers who mostly resorted to almost absolute fictionalization, the third generation are often daring in their characterizations, especially when dealing with historical issues. If Chinua Achebe – a remarkable first generation Nigerian writer were to belong to the third generation, the character of Chief Nanga in *A Man of the People* would have probably taken the full or part of the name of a notable Nigerian politician in view of his characterisation in the novel.

When, in reference to the characters of Ifemelu and her estranged American partner Blaine, the narrator observes that “...they had survived the fight, mostly because of Barack Obama, bonding anew over their shared passion. On election night... he held her tightly as though Obama’s victory was also their personal victory” (p.7), Adichie implies that Obama’s presidential candidacy and possible electoral victory serves as a veritable healing, unifying and conciliatory element in a strained relationship. She uses this scenario to portray how the euphoria surrounding the possibility of a black man being elected to the White House somehow galvanised and unified several Americans from all races and colours. Our next meeting with Obama’s electoral issues in the novel is at a conversation at a dinner party in Manhattan where an Obama supporter, a white man, excitedly states that “Obama will end racism in this country” (*Americanah*, p.290). And it is a cheering expression to the guests at the party. The narrator goes on to mention the name of Barack Obama’s actual spouse “Michelle Obama” (p.296) and to use her in typical discourses in the context of racism and American political culture. Again, it is obvious that the delineation of the character of Michelle Obama as Barack Obama’s spouse in the novel is in conformity with reality. In doing this, Adichie seemed to have broken the boundary between artistic production and historical traces. Most of the historical issues bordering on race and identify politics in the novel are however revealed through Ifemelu’s blogs. She writes:

His pastor is scary because it means maybe Obama is not the Magic Negro after all. ... but have you been to an old school American Black Church? Pure theatre. But the guys basic point is true: that American Blacks (certainly those his age) know an America different from American Whites; they know a harsher, uglier America. But you’re not supposed to say that, because in America everything is fine. ...and if Obama thinks so then he isn’t the Magic Negro and only a Magic Negro can win an American election. And what’s a Magic Negro, you ask? The black man who is eternally wise and kind. He never reacts under great suffering, never gets angry, is never threatening. He always forgives all kinds of racist shit. He teaches the white person how to break down the sad but understandable prejudice in his heart. You see this man in many films. An Obama is straight from central casting. (*Americanah*, p.321)

The issues of racism and identify politics in the United States are historical issues which have been in existence for centuries. Adichie uses the instrumentality of literature to subtly interrogate this in the context of the emergence of the first black man, Barack Obama as a Democratic Presidential hopeful in 2008. It is in view of this that McCoy (2018, p.279) states:

Americanah (2013) re-imagines racial solidarity between African immigrants of the “new” African diaspora and African American of the “old” African diaspora. Adichie’s counter-narratives offers a cultural insider a “valid source of knowledge” for interrogating cultural hegemony in the US. The novel’s protagonist Ifemelu, and her anonymously authored blog, which contains cultural commentary on race relations in the US form the perspective of an African immigrants... Through her blog, Ifemelu rhetorically signals racial solidarity with African American, but the protagonist also

divulges how average white American readers assume that all blacks regardless of national origin share in the same experience of blackness.

When at a point in the debate and contest for either Hillary Clinton or Obama ticket in the Democratic Party Ifemelu says, “I like Hillary Clinton. I don’t really know anything about this Obama guy” (p.329), Adichie suggests that not all blacks in America, after all, endorse Obama’s presidential aspiration despite the fact that blacks in America have been suffering centuries of racial injustices. That, of course, demonstrates the beauty of democracy as exemplified in the United States at that remarkable point in history. Still reminiscing on the price black Americans paid and continue to pay on account of racism in the US, Ifemelu blogs thus: “Barack Obama, looking as he does, would have had to sit in the back of the bus fifty years ago. If a random black guy commits a crime today, Barack Obama could be stopped and questioned for fitting in the profile. And what would that profile be? Black man” (p.338).

Ifemelu, however, becomes Obama’s staunch supporter and fan when she encounters him in his globally acclaimed autobiography, *Dreams From My Father*, as the narrator states:

At first, even though she wished America would elect a black man as president, she thought it impossible, and she could not imagine Obama as president of the United States; he seemed too slight, too skinny, a man who would be blown away by the wind. Hillary Clinton was sturdier. Ifemelu liked to watch Clinton on television... She wished her victory, willed good fortune her way, until the morning she picked up Barack Obama’s book, *Dreams From My Father*, which Blaine had just finished... She examined the photographs on the cover, the young Kenyan woman staring befuddled at the camera, arms enclosing her son, and the young American man, jaunty of manner, holding his daughter to his chest. She read *Dreams From My Father* in a day and a half, sitting up on the couch...she was absorbed and moved by the man she met in those pages, an enquiring and intelligent man, a kind man, a man so utterly, helplessly, winningly humane... she believed Barack Obama. (*Americanah*, p.353)

It is on account of this singular encounter that Ifemelu declares her total and unalloyed support for Obama’s aspiration when she says, “If only the man who wrote this book could be the president of America” (p.353). The narrator would state that subsequently,

Every morning, Ifemelu woke up and checked to make sure that Obama was still alive. That no scandal had emerged, no story dug up from his past. She would turn on her computer, her breath still, her heart frantic in her chest, and then reassured that he was alive, she would read the latest news about him, quickly and greedily, seeking information and reassurance, multiple windows minimized at the bottom of the screen. Sometimes, in chat rooms, she wilted as she read the posts about Obama and she would get up and move away from her computer, as though the laptop itself were the enemy, and stand by the window to hide her tears even from herself. How can a monkey be president? Somebody do us a favour and put a bullet in this guy. Send him back to the African jungle. A black man will never be in the White House, dude, it’s called the White House for a reason. (*Americanah*, p.353-354)

By the delineation of the characters of Barack Obama, Hillary Clinton, Michelle Obama, Oprah Winfrey (p.356) and also in citing the title of Obama’s real autobiography, *Dreams From My Father*, and raising some exact issues contained therein in connection with the heated debates of America’s presidential election of 2008, Adichie does not just follow the path of historical accuracy but also

pushes her novelistic endeavours to the realm of what some critics would refer to as fiction. The same thing can be said of her allusion to the tragic death of “Princess Diana” (p.232) of Wales on 31 August, 1997. Concerning the incident, *Wikipedia* (2020) documents:

In the early hours of 31 August 1997, Diana, princess of Wales died in hospital after being injured in a car crash in a road tunnel in Paris. Her partner Dodi Fayed, and their driver, Henri Paul, were pronounced dead at the scene.... Some media claimed the erratic behaviour of paparazzi following the car, as reported by the BBC, had contributed to the crash. (“Princess Diana”)

In alluding to this historical development in reference to the arranged marriage between the fictional characters of Okoli Okafor and Crystal Smith in England, the narrator states:

Now here he was, a ghost of a name, about to get married in England. Perhaps it was also a marriage for papers. Okoli Okafor. Everyone called him Okoli Paparazzi in University. On the day Princess Diana died, a group of students had gathered before a lecture, talking about what they had heard on the radio that morning, repeating “paparazzi” over and over, all sounding knowing and cocksure, until, in a lull, Okoli Okafor quietly said, “but who exactly are the paparazzi? Are they motorcyclists?” and instantly earned himself the nickname Okoli Paparazzi. (*Americanah*, p.232)

Okoli Okafor is Obinze’s schoolmate who emigrates to England from Nigeria “...during one of the long strikes” (p.232) for an undocumented existence in London. He is however planning to take a British wife in order to possibly facilitate his documentation and consolidate his stay in London “now that Blunkett is after them”(p.231). The ultimate aim for such a marriage is often to secure the much elusive national security number that will enable such an immigrant to work legally. Obinze is on a similar mission at the Marriage Registry when he unexpectedly sees Okoli's name as the narrator states: “Behind the desk a whiteboard was propped on a wall, venues and dates of intended marriages written on it in blue; a name at the bottom caught his eye. Okoli Okafor and Crystal Smith” (p.231).

It can be recalled that prolonged industrial actions in Nigerian tertiary institutions in the 1980s and 1990s under the military regimes of Generals Ibrahim Babangida and Sani Abacha were a regular occurrence. It was not only Nigerian intellectuals who emigrated to the more stable West in droves but also many parents, after waiting in vain for several months for resumption of tertiary institutions, withdrew their children and sent them overseas either to continue with their education or to “hustle.” In *Americanah* (2013, p.98), the situation is further captured thus:

In the newspapers, University lecturers listed their complaints, the agreements that were trampled in the dust by government men whose own children were schooling abroad. Campuses were emptied, classrooms drained of life. Students hoped for short strikes, because they could not hope to have no strike at all. Everyone was talking about leaving.

These are the social and historical circumstances Adichie largely demonstrates and historicizes in *Americanah*. The narrator also makes a vivid historical allusion in deploying the lexical item “paparazzi” in connection with part of the cause of death of Princess Diana of Wales for in historical reality, the word “paparazzi” was constantly on air when the death of the princess was announced to the world on August 31st 1997. These independent photographers who take and document the pictures of high profile people and celebrities, often while such personalities go about their usual life routines were reported to have been “erratic” in the manner in which they followed the princess’ car just before the

accident in a road tunnel in Paris. Her partner, Dodi Fayed, and their driver, Henri Paul died in a hospital from injuries sustained from the crash.

On the Nigerian socio-historical scene, Adichie in *Americanah* as in *Purple Hibiscus* historicises a number of occurrences during the dictatorial regimes of Generals Babangida and Abacha, and goes further to interrogate certain questionable economic and political developments under the civilian administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo which lasted from 1999 to 2007. Also, just as in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, characterisation and allusions to historical figures and issues are partially veiled as Adichie elects to use the actual names of such historical figures and even discusses some quite notable historical developments under their watch. Some of the portrayed actions and inactions of these national leaders are, however, indicting. Adichie uses such indictments to remind leaders even in contemporary times that there is an inevitable judgment of history for every action and inaction while in office as a leader or a ruler.

Adichie begins her insightful investigation and exploration of Nigerian historical developments in *Americanah* with a demonstration of the futility of primitive accumulation of public wealth and consequent institutional collapse as experienced during the failed banks saga under the regime of General Sani Abacha who ruled the country between 1993 and 1998. The historical incident is reflected through the utterances of a character simply identified as Chief on the occasion of the visit of Obinze and his cousin Nneoma to the Chief's residence for a possible assistance to the unemployed Obinze.

After his guests left, Chief turned to Nneoma. "Do you know that song 'No One Knows Tomorrow?'" Then he proceeded to sing the song with childish gusto. *No One Knows Tomorrow! To-mor-row! No One Knows Tomorrow!...* "That is the one principle that this country is based on... Remember those big bankers during Abacha's government? They thought they owned this country, and the next thing they knew, they were in prison. Look at that pauper who could not pay his rent before, then Babangida gave him an oil well, and now he has a private jet!" Chief spoke with a triumphant tone... while Nneoma listened and smiled and agreed. Her animation was exaggerated, as though a bigger smile and a quicker laugh... would ensure that Chief would help them. (*Americanah*, p.24-25)

This is a profound artistic investigation of vivid historical developments in Nigeria. By this representation, Adichie suggests that Babangida's "settlement" approach as a leader cannot be said to be wholesome and exemplary, and that Abacha's setting up of a Failed Banks Tribunal during his regime might not have been altogether done with altruistic and patriotic intentions. Bach et al. (2001) corroborate the historical circumstances thus:

What Babangida started, Abacha deepened and consolidated. Babangida's iron-fisted autocracy pales into relative insignificance, indeed almost becomes a benevolent dictatorship, compared to the executive brigandage that characterised the Abacha government. By unleashing a state-sponsored brutality on real and imagined opponents – in politics, banking... There was equally the Failed Banks Tribunal set up to investigate thieving bank chieftains, but which soon degenerated into a witch-hunt.

In Nigeria's political history, several events in the regimes of the two Generals actually marked the peak of military dictatorship and perfidy as Adichie demonstrates in *Americanah* as she earlier did in *Purple Hibiscus*. While Abacha is associated with Failed Banks Tribunal which, instead of serving altruistic purposes metamorphosed to a witch-hunt and repressive tool in his hand, Babangida's unparalleled "settlement philosophy" is foregrounded. Babangida till today remains one Nigerian

leader historically associated with a “settlement” ideology. This is essentially the issue Adichie raises in the novel when, through the character Chief, it is stated that “Babangida gave him an oil well” in reference to a pauper who becomes super-rich over night to the point of purchasing a private jet. Adichie, however, does not state the reason for the generous gift of an oil well (a state asset) from Babangida to the unnamed individual. And by adducing no reasons, she seems to be questioning the motive behind the mouth-watering gift – a huge asset which constitutionally belongs to the entire nation being given to one man by the Head of State. But such is a demonstration of the unbridled corrupt and nepotistic propensities that characterised the Nigerian ruler in his time in history (1985 – 1993). Also, by closely situating the two incidents in the text – Abacha’s witch-hunting Failed Banks Tribunal and Babangida’s settlement ideology – Adichie suggests that the former dictatorship is as retrogressive and devastating as the latter. Fayemi’s (1999, p.70) observations in this regard are even more revealing:

The Nigerian economy did not escape Abacha’s grip. He ran it as a personal fiefdom. Unlike Babangida who parceled out the state to friends and mentors within the military, Abacha kept the spoils of office for himself and his family, a small coterie of his security apparatus and his small circle of foreign friends.

It is perhaps for its inclination to “give out an oil well” - a state asset, for the corrupt enrichment of a single man as Adichie (2013) states or “parceling out the state to friends” as Fayemi (2001) observes that the Babangida administration is usually tagged as the administration that institutionalized corruption in the country. And if Babangida’s government institutionalized corruption, Abacha’s was certainly a daylight robbery and looting of the national treasury for ironically, while Abacha set up the Failed Banks Tribunal which tried and jailed some chief executives of failed banks for financial impropriety, he himself was busy stealing the country blind. Twenty-two years after his demise, millions of dollars are still being recovered and repatriated from several foreign countries including America as part of Abacha loot.

Again, it is through the character of Chief - a typical nepotistic, acquisitive and corrupt Nigerian politician and capitalist that Adichie interrogates President Olusegun Obasanjo's privatisation programme. Adichie believes that the programme lacks transparency, is riddled with corruption and is a means through which the nation’s politicians and their cronies fraudulently enrich themselves to the detriment of the poor masses who become poorer while the rich become richer. Adichie states that “Chief was his usual garrulous self” (p.26) on a certain occasion of Obinze’s visit to his home in search of economic assistance. Then Chief reveals: “I was Babangida’s friend. I was Abacha’s friend. Now that the military has gone, Obasanjo is my friend. Do you know why? Is it because I am stupid?” (p.26). When Obinze, of course, expectedly responds in the negative, Chief goes on to make more startling and indicting revelations:

They said the National Farm Support Corporation is bankrupt and they’re going to privatize it. Do you know this? No. How do I know this? Because I have friends. By the time you know it, I would have taken a position and I would have benefited from the arbitrage. That is our free market! The corporation was set up in the sixties and it owns property everywhere. The houses are all rotten and termites are eating the roofs. But they are selling them. I am going to buy seven properties for five million each. You know what they are listed for in the books? One million. You know what the real worth is? Fifty million. I need somebody to front this deal. (*Americanah*, p.26)

In reality, the privatisation programme which commenced in 1999 after Obasanjo took over as president till today continues to raise more questions than answers. *Premium Times* newspaper issue of

Sunday, June 14, 2020 still reports that a group known as Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) is still urging President Muhammadu Buhari to use his “good offices and leadership position to revisit and refer allegations of corruption and abuse of process in the privatisation of public enterprises in Nigeria between 1999-2011 to the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission and the Independent Corrupt practices and Other Related Offenses Commission for further investigation.” The request and position of the group, according to *Premium Times* is based on its privileged access to the Senate Ad-Hoc Committee Report that was earlier involved in the investigation of the matter. According to Mr Adetokunbo Mumuni, the leader of the group as quoted in *Premium Times*,

SERAP has obtained and carefully read the full report of the Senate Ad-Hoc Committee on Investigation of the Privatisation and Commercialization Activities of the Bureau of Public Enterprise (BPE) from 1999 to 2011, which contains damaging allegations of corruption, presidential interference, and abuse of due process in the selection of core investor, valuation of Public enterprises, pricing of shares/assets, determination of workers terminal benefits, and use of proceeds of privatisation. (*Premium Times*, June 14, 2020)

Adichie uses the character of Chief in *Americanah* to strategically cast aspersion and interrogate the manner in which this historical privatisation programme was conducted to the disgust of many Nigerians. In a report titled “How Obasanjo and Atiku Destroyed Nigeria's Privatisation Process” – a *Sahara Reporters* issue of August 12, 2011, the online news agency notes that “Former President Olusegun Obasanjo and his deputy, Atiku Abubakar, may have influenced the sales of government enterprises to their friends.” This opinion according to *Sahara Reporters* is predicated on the “revelations” of Mallam Nasir El-Rufai –a former Director General of Bureau For Public Enterprise (BPE) before the aforementioned Senate Ad-Hoc Committee when he was invited during investigations. El-Rufai is quoted to have said that “the president and I were always quarreling over issues of privatization. Each time I told him we have a process... that they should advise their friends to be the highest bidder.”

These are the socioeconomic and historical circumstances Adichie historicizes in the novel through the character Chief, as well as through the use of names of some real historical figures and leaders as demonstrated. Yet Adichie is not altogether critical of President Obasanjo’s administration. In a seemingly commendable tone, some of the achievements of his government are remembered and stated on the occasion of Obinze’s mother’s encouragement to her son when he is consistently frustrated in the labour market after graduating with a good grade from the university and his visa application at the US Embassy equally failed, a consequence of post 9/11:

He was living with his mother, driving her car... He disliked her calm good cheer, how hard she tried to be positive, telling him that now President Obasanjo was in power, things were changing; the mobile phone companies and banks were growing and recruiting, even giving young people car loans. (*Americanah*, p.233-234)

This note of commendation is earlier amplified when Ifemelu’s father in a phone conversation with her says, “One could not describe Obasanjo as a good man, but it must be conceded that he has done some good things in the country; there is a flourishing spirit of entrepreneurship” (p. 201).

Adichie also makes a veiled allusion to Major Gideon Gwaza Orkar's failed coup d’etat of 22nd April, 1990 when she writes:

On the day of the coup, a close friend of the General called to ask if she was with him. There was tension; some army officers had already been arrested. Auntie Uju was not

with the General, did not know where he was.... Finally, The General called to say that he was fine, the coup had failed and all was well with the Head of State. (*Americanah*, p.80-81)

Although Nigeria had a number of both successful and unsuccessful coups in the past, and, of course, Adichie has historicized some of them in her previous novels as earlier stated, this particular coup re-echoes that led by Major Orkar in April 1990 against the Babangida regime for a number of reasons stated in his speech. Orkar's coup remains one of the bloodiest, both during and after the putsch in Nigeria's coup history. In view of the historical time and administrations the novel reflects, anyone familiar with the history of coups in the country knows that it is a clear reference to the Orkar coup. It is the coup which shook the very foundation of the Babangida regime as the General was almost toppled. The narrator narrows down the coup allusion to the Babangida regime when she reveals how The General eventually dies:

The General died the next week, in a military plane crash. It was on a Saturday afternoon. ...The General's ADC, crackled through a bad connection, but was still clear enough to give her details: the crash happened a few miles outside Jos, the bodies were charred, there were already rumours that the Head of State had engineered it to get rid of officers who he feared were planning a coup. (*Americanah*, p.86)

A plane crash involving mainly middle ranking and a few high ranking officers occurred during the Babangida regime (1985-1993) with the same kind of rumour – "...the Head of State had engineered it to get rid of officers who he feared were planning a coup." This is a historical rumour associated with the Babangida regime especially with regards to the military plane crash that occurred during the era. Again, with respect to the notable military action of April 22, 1990, which is similar to what Adichie depicts in *Americanah*, *Wikipedia* (2020) states:

Major Gideon Gwaza Orkar (October 4, 1952 – July 27, 1990) was a Nigerian military officer who staged a violent coup against the government of General Ibrahim Babangida on April 22, 1990. Orkar and his conspirators seized the FRCN radio station, various military posts around Lagos and the Dodan Barracks, Lagos, the military headquarters and presidential residence. Babangida was present when the barracks were attacked but managed to escape by a route. In his coup address, Orkar called for the excision of five northern states. However, the coup was crushed by the Babangida regime and Orkar was executed... Major Orkar and 41 other conspirators were convicted of treason and executed by firing squad on July 27th, 1990 by the government of General Ibrahim Babangida. ("Gideon Orkar")

Also, concerning the military plane crash on a "Saturday" under the Babangida regime which Adichie profoundly alludes to in *Americanah*, *The New York Times* magazine issue of September 28, 1992 with the caption, "163 Nigerians Dead As a Military Plane Crashes Near Lagos" states:

A Nigerian military transport plane crashed soon after take off from Lagos, killing all 163 people aboard... Many of those killed on Saturday night in the crash of the Hercules C-130 were believed to be middle-ranking army, navy and airforce officers attending a staff college course in Northern Nigeria.... The plane crash was Nigeria's worst air disaster since 1973, when a royal Jordanian Airlines Boeing 707 burst into flames on landing at Kano, another city in the North, killing 176 people. ...many of the dead were believed to have been officers taking a course at the Nigerian Command and Staff College at Jaji, in northern Kaduna State, and that some others of them were instructors.

Adichie reflects reality with this significant event when, among other things, she states that the plane crash which claims the life of “The General” and other persons occurred on a “Saturday” (p.86) for in reality the historical plane crash occurred on Saturday, 26th September, 1992. *Los Angeles Times* adds a dimension to the report on the same September 28, 1992 which the *New York Times* equally reported the incident, when it corroborates thus:

A military transport plane crashed into a swamp shortly after take off from Lagos, and all 163 army officers, relatives and crew members on board were killed... The crash occurred Saturday evening but was not discovered until Sunday morning, when bodies were found floating in the swamp outside Lagos. The Hercules C-130 aircraft disappeared from the radar of Lagos' Murtala Muhammed Airport three minutes after take off at 5 p.m. Saturday. Many of the passengers aboard the plane were officers of a military college in Jaji Town who had gone to Lagos for a navy celebration.

Adichie's mention that “...the crash happened a few miles outside Jos” (*Americanah*, p. 86) is a mimicry and reflection of Nowa Omoigu's (1998) detailed factual account of the incident entitled “The Crash of NAF 911 on September 26, 1992” where it is stated that,

Much of the morning of Saturday, September 26, 1992 was dominated by activities related to environmental sanitation. Shortly before 1730 hrs a Nigerian Airforce Military Transport plane, a Lockheed C-130H-LM HERCULES (L-82), production number 4624, registration number NAF 911, piloted by Wing Commanders J.P. Alabesunu and A.S. Mamadi finally got the okay from the control towers to take off – enroute to Kaduna and Jos in the northern part of the country. From the Kaduna airport, its unique passengers planned to make their way by road back to the Command and Staff College in Jaji. Consisting predominantly of middle-ranking officers drawn from the 19th, 20th, and 21st regular courses of the Nigerian Defence Academy, accompanied by a few from the 18th course along with some foreign students, they had been in Lagos on a Naval tour as part of the senior division course.

The “...rumours that the Head of State had engineered it [the plane crash] to get rid of officers who he feared were planning a coup”(p.86) as stated by Adichie could have been fueled by, again, Omoigu's factual account; what actually, among other suspicions, prompted many Nigerians at the period of that ugly historical incident to think and believe that a powerful official's hand was behind the crash. Omoigu (1998) observes that although the aircraft had disappeared from the radar and reportedly crashed at 17.35hrs after taking off from the Murtala Muhammed International Airport Lagos at about 17.30 hrs – Just about five minutes after it took off on Saturday, 26 September, 1992,

No organized rescue effort was arranged within a time frame that would have meant anything to the victims of the crash. However, it is clear that the control tower knew something had gone wrong and notified the Airport Commandant. At about 8p.m., Lt Colonel Kayode Are, one of the Directing Staff at the Command and Staff College in Jaji, placed a long distance call to his course-mate in Lagos, Lt. Colonel Owoye Azazi, CO of the Intelligence Group at the Lagos Garrison to get information about the crash. Azazi...placed a call to Captain Al Mustapha, Chief Security Officer to Lt. General Sani Abacha, who was at that time Chief of Defence Staff... However, no orders were forthcoming from Abacha on whether or how to respond... Therefore, early on Sunday morning, General Adisa, Commodore Akhigbe, Lt. Col. Azazi and Captain Deinde Joseph set off for the Air Force Base. They were told that the plane crashed a few minutes after take off... There were reports of scribbled notes by some of the survivors,

indicating that they survived the initial impact... On Monday, the Head of the Lagos Garrison Intelligence group reportedly spoke with the US Defence Attache about the possibility of sending Chinook Helicopters to help. However, the rather curious response of the Nigerian Army High Command – as communicated by the Military Assistant to Lt. General Salihu Ibrahim, then Chief of Army Staff, was that for reasons of national pride, a request for foreign help was not appropriate. The details of how “national pride” became a reason to delay recovery of our fallen heroes at that stage are best explained by those involved – and those they were reporting to at higher levels i.e Generals Abacha and Babangida.

Omoigu (1998) goes on to justify one of the basis for his assertions by quoting a respected Nigerian journalist and newspaper columnist, Remi Oyeyemi who documents that,

It is on record that in less than an hour of the crash, the British government offered to rescue the victims and the offer was turned down by IBB. It is also on record that the U.S. government informed the IBB administration that they had a ship on the high seas very close to Nigeria that could be on the scene within few hours of the crash to help in the rescue effort. It was turned down by IBB.

Indeed, the ugly historical incident of September 26, 1992 till today leaves more questions than answers. Although General Abacha is now dead and cannot defend himself for any level of culpability, Babangida is still alive and aging. He is yet to see any need to, if the rumour is false, clear the air and perhaps absolve himself from any form of culpability. To continue to keep mute in the face of such grave allegation and rumour of orchestrating the crushing and silencing of over 163 destinies at the prime of their lives is to, nonetheless, give validity to it. That a young writer like Adichie can use the instrumentality of literature to interrogate the event 21 years after the occurrence is a pointer to the fact that the matter will continue to generate national debate and discourse until the principal accused person like Babangida possibly speaks out to clear the air; otherwise the judgment of history may not be in his favour so long as the issue and such other matters are concerned. A popular Igbo proverb states that he who keeps silent has already concurred. This is to say that Babangida’s silence over this matter 28 years after he left office can be interpreted by many as acquiescence and absolute culpability as “rumoured.”

Adichie, again, raises a thorny historical issue when in a particular conversational episode involving the characters Bartholomew and Aunty Uju, Bartholomew asserts that “Kudirat’s death will not be in vain, it will only galvanize the democratic movement in a way that even her life did not! I just wrote an article about the issue online in *Nigerian Village*” (*Americanah*, p.116).

This is a historical allusion to the death of Kudirat Abiola, the late wife of Chief M.K.O. Abiola the acclaimed winner of June 12, 1993 presidential election in Nigeria. The said election in Nigeria remains globally acclaimed as the freest and fairest in the nation’s political history. But the mandate was never actualized because it was annulled by the Babangida administration under whose watch and supervision the election was conducted. Upon Babangida’s “stepping aside” and Abacha’s ascension to power, Abiola was arrested and incarcerated by Abacha on his insistence to realize his mandate. It was upon his incarceration that his wife Kudirat stepped up her protest alongside other pro-democracy forces in the country, both for the release of her husband and for the actualization of June 12 mandate. Consequently, she was perceived as a threat by the Abacha junta. She was gunned down in a street in Lagos on June 4, 1996. *Wikipedia* (2020) captures the incident thus:

Alhaja Kudirat Abiola, popularly known simply as Kudirat Abiola, was a Nigerian pro-democracy campaigner. She was assassinated while her husband, Moshood Abiola, was being detained by the Nigerian government. He was the winning candidate in elections that had taken place in Nigeria in 1993, and was arrested shortly after they were summarily annulled by the ruling junta. (“Kudirat Abiola”)

This account is corroborated by Obi-Ani (2019) when she states:

Kudirat Abiola...led the struggle to actualize and re-validate the June 12, 1993 presidential election. The General Sani Abacha regime was prepared to silence all opposition to the annulled election and spared no effort in targeting the arrowheads such as NADECO and Civil Rights Organizations in the country. Despite the imminent danger to her life, Kudirat Abiola mobilized all social, cultural and even political groups to oppose the military stand on June 12, 1993 election. Even when it became clear that the military will go beyond threat to assassination, she never budged. Many opposition political leaders were eliminated yet Kudirat Abiola was prepared to fight for her husband’s rights. It was in the process of seeking justice for her husband’s annulled presidential election that she was fatally shot in broad daylight on June 4, 1996.

Bartholomew’s assertion in *Americanah* that “Kudirat’s death will not be in vain...” (p.116) is however, a prophecy which has come to fulfillment for barely a year after Abiola's death in incarceration, on 7 July, 1998, the several years of pro-democracy struggles of people like Kudirat culminated in the restoration of democratic order in Nigeria on May 29, 1999. A number of national monuments including a tertiary institution and Abuja National Stadium have been named after her husband, Chief M.K.O Abiola, whose annulled presidential mandate she gallantly fought for and eventually paid with her own life. Also, on June 6, 2018, Abiola was posthumously awarded the highest title of honour in Nigeria – GCFR by President Muhammadu Buhari's administration and Nigeria’s democracy day was changed to June 12, all in recognition of the democratic struggles of people like Kudirat and Abiola himself. Indeed, Kudirat’s death is not in vain.

Adichie mythologises the historic execution, by firing squad, of a notorious Nigerian bandit on 29th March, 1987 in Benin City in the present day Edo State when she states:

In primary school, Ifemelu had watched the firing squad that killed Lawrence Anini, fascinated by the mythologies around his armed robberies, how he wrote warning letters to newspapers, fed the poor with what he stole, turned himself into air when the police came. Her mother had said, “Go inside, this is not for children,” but half-heartedly, after Ifemelu had already seen most of the shooting anyway, Anini’s body roughly tied to a pole, jerking as the bullets hit him, before slumping against the criss-cross of rope. (*Americanah*, p.148)

As she has elected to do in *Americanah*, the exact name of this notorious historical character Lawrence Anini is used in conformity with the ignoble role he played at a period in history. Anini robbed and terrorised financial institutions as well as other citizens in Benin City and its environs almost to the utter helplessness of security forces. Concerning Anini and his notorious activities, *Wikipedia* (2020) documents:

Lawrence Nomanyagbon Anini (C.1960 – March 29, 1987) was a Nigerian bandit who terrorized Benin City in the 1980s along with his sidekick Monday Osunbor. He was captured and executed for his crimes. Lawrence Anini was born in a village about 30 kilometers (20 mi) from Benin City in the present-day Edo State. He later dived into the

criminal business and soon became a driver and transporter for gangs, criminal godfathers and thieves. In August, 1986, a fatal bank robbery linked to Anini was reported in which a police officer and a child were killed. That same month, two officers on duty were shot at a barricade while trying to stop Anini's car. During a span of three months, he was known to have killed 9 police officers. He wrote numerous letters to media houses using political tones of Robin Hook-like words to describe his criminal acts. Anini was once believed to be a spirit in possession of magical powers; it was also believed that he could teleport at will. On December 3, 1986, he was caught at a house in Benin City. The country's military leader, Ibrahim Babangida, demanded a speedy trial. Anini was convicted of most of his charges and was executed on March 29, 1987. ("Lawrence Anini")

In the 1980s, the name Anini was a popular metaphor for crime and criminality such that any young person found to have a propensity for nefarious activities, particularly in schools, was usually branded an Anini. Many equally feared the name since the notorious Anini was widely speculated to be in possession of some magical powers; the ability to teleport – to appear and disappear at will. Igbinovia (1998, p.131) states:

...Anini, 26 years old was Nigeria's most notorious armed robber. His image was larger than life, dwarfing those of Ishola Oyenusi, the king of robbers in the 1970s and Youpelle Dakuro, the army deserter who masterminded the most vicious daylight robbery in Lagos in 1978 in which two policemen were killed. Anini spear-headed a four-month reign of terror between August and December 1986 that gripped...Nigeria. While he and his gang reigned, they killed, maimed, kidnapped, robbed and raped their victims. The episodes were replicated with increasing sophistication, brazenness and arrogance. At the end of it all, 20 persons – 11 policemen and 9 civilians were dead.

Indeed, Anini's siege on Nigeria was a nightmare and a metaphor for horror. Igbinovia (1998,) also concurs that Justice Omo-Agege, the Chairman of the First Benin Robbery and Firearms Tribunal which tried and sentenced Anini and his cohorts, aptly stated it when he wrote that "Anini will forever be remembered in the history of crime in this country, but it would be of unblessed memory. Few people if ever, would give the name to their children" (In Igbinovia, 1998, P.31).

By the manner of her portrayal of Anini's lifestyle in *Americanah*, it is clear that Adichie believes that his eventual fate (death by firing squad) is justice well deserved and served for his notoriety and atrocities, and that his act of "feeding the poor with what he stole" (p.148) cannot in any way justify his criminality and violence. Thus the historicisation of the notorious character Lawrence Anini in *Americanah* is both a condemnation of crime, violence and criminality as well as a veritable warning to all mortals of ill-motives and nefarious propensities, no matter how mystical, powerful or even successful they may seem to be at the beginning of such ignoble enterprise. Otwin (1987, p.259) agrees to this view when he states that Anini's final fate as a bandit was a "Face to Face with the Law."

Furthermore, Adichie's allusions to the election of Alhaji Shehu Shagari in 1979 as well as certain issues surrounding the life and time of the legendary Afro musician Fela Anikulapo Kuti are rather cursory when she narrates:

Don looked into Ifemelu's eye and told her how he had nearly visited Nigeria, just after Shagari was elected, when he worked as a consultant to an international development agency, but the trip fell through at the last minute and he had felt bad because he had been hoping to go to the shrine and see Fela perform. He mentioned Fela casually,

intimately; as though it was something they had in common, a secret they shared. (*Americanah*, p.150)

Both Shagari and Fela are historical figures whose portrayals in the novel conform with both historical and contemporary realities for although President Shagari had ruled between 1979 until 31st December, 1983 when he was overthrown by Major General Muhammadu Buhari, the famous Fela's shrine is still being maintained by his descendants and remains a place of attraction for many foreign nationals as well as Nigerian citizens from all walks of life. Just like Don, an American citizen who wants to visit the shrine in order to see Fela perform” (p.150) but for the reason that “the trip fell through at the last minute,” President Emmanuel Macron of France actually visited the shrine on July 3rd, 2018. *Wikipedia* (2020) documents that,

The New Afrika Shrine is an open air entertainment center located in Ikeja, Lagos State. It serves as the host location of the annual Felabration music festival. Currently managed by Femi Kuti (eldest son of Fela Kuti) and Yeni Anikulapo- Kuti, it is the replacement of the old Afrika Shrine created in 1970 by Fela Kuti... The New Afrika Shrine showcases photo galleries of Fela and music performances by Femi Kuti and Seun Kuti thus making it a tourist attraction. On July 3rd, 2018, French President Emmanuel Macron visited the shrine and pre-launched the Season of African Cultures 2020 in France. Macron said he had visited the shrine as a student in 2002. (“New Afrika Shrine”)

There is also a reminiscence of the euphoria that greeted the death of General Sani Abacha in several quarters on June 8, 1998 as well as General Muhammadu Buhari’s brutal and repressive regime of the early eighties when in connection with the experiences of Obinze and his professor mother the narrator states:

Once during his final year in the University, the year that people danced in the streets because General Abacha had died, his mother had said... as though her friends who were leaving for teaching positions in Canada and America had confirmed to her a great personal failure. ...While Andrew was checking out, General Buhari’s soldiers were flogging adults in the streets, lecturers were striking for better pay, and his mother had decided that he could no longer have Fanta whenever he wanted but only on Sundays, with permission. (*Americanah*, p.232)

The celebration as occasioned by the death of General Abacha in the excerpt is predicated on the harsh political and economic realities the nation faced under his regime. This situation prompts a large number of intellectuals who are Obinze’s mother’s colleagues to massively emigrate to mainly Canada and America where they envisage better conditions for their needed services. Nigeria is in turmoil under a dictator named General Abacha, and their salaries as university lecturers are hardly paid let alone allowances, or even maintain the institutional infrastructure. Although Obinze’s mother decides to remain in the country while facing the harsh and traumatic economic realities caused by Abacha’s misgovernance, she does not conceal her perception of forlornly in the entire situation. But her son, Obinze, is insistent on emigrating to America in search of greener pastures after graduating from the university, although “...he knew how unreasonable the American embassy could be – the vice chancellor, of all people, had once been refused a visa to attend a conference – but he had never doubted his plan”(p.232). It is amidst this chaotic situation the country is facing that the ruler, Abacha, who carries the blame for all the woes the country is going through suddenly dies, and on this premise “...people danced in the streets” with the mindset that the ordeals the nation is passing through under

his dictatorship will equally die along with him. In his *The Last 100 Days of Abacha*, Adeniyi (2005, p.228) notes:

The sad thing is that General Abacha so much dehumanised Nigerians that the nation that mourned the death of General Murtala Muhammed in 1976 as if he was a member of everyone's family trooped to the streets last week to rejoice about the demise of its leader. How will history remember Abacha? – Ken Saro- Wiwa, Kudirat Abiola, Shehu Yar'Adua, not to talk of Olusegun Obasanjo, Ibrahim Dasuki and Chris Anyanwu. All of these persons, dead or alive, are the testimony to Abacha's reign of terror. Perhaps only questionable characters who were ready to say 'no-one-but-you' prospered from his regime. He personalized the state and its resources. At the end, he was buried like any other commoner. With nothing. He preyed on our fears but he can no longer do anything. Dead. And buried!

Adeniyi's rhetorical question, "How will history remember Abacha?" is already partly answered in his representations in Adichie's *Americanah* and even *Purple Hibiscus*, a clear attestation to William Shakespeare's age long assertion that the evil that men do live after them. In *Americanah*– a novel written 15 years after his death, Abacha's depictions remain that of a villainous despot who almost suffocated to death the country he was privileged to become it's leader. It is in view of this that Adeniyi (2005, p.228), again, in a direct reference to General Abacha says, "Here was a man on whom history placed so much opportunities to go down as a hero yet he squandered all. He chose to be obstinate against positive current." In the postscript in Adeniyi's stated book on Abacha, Colonel Abubakar Umar, a former military governor of Kaduna State re-echoes the popular testimony about the person of General Abacha when he states:

The Abacha years in Nigeria were, no doubt, a tragic period in the political history of our nation. While General Abacha is dead, and hence now carries the blame for all our socio-economic and political misfortunes, people who can reflect on that era must remember that he had many willing, and even eager collaborators for his tyrannical 'transition programme' which ruthlessly imposed deceit, terror and violence on the citizenry. (p.233)

Indeed, Abacha's reign of terror over two decades ago has become a multidisciplinary research issue attracting scholars from areas such as Political Science, Sociology, Education, Literature, History and so on. Needless to say that Adichie equally uses Abacha's representations in her novels to convey some vital messages and warnings to contemporary Nigerian leaders who in one way or the other continue to emulate Abacha's style of leadership, particularly in the area of looting public treasury and high-handedness. In his report on May 14, 2020 issue of *Vanguard* newspaper captioned "Nigeria Shames Itself By Posthumously Honouring Abacha" Olu Fasan maintains that,

Sani Abacha, Nigeria's Kleptomaniac and despotic former dictator died... But if anything reminds us of him, it is Shakespeare's famous words: 'The evil that men do lives after them.' For 22 years after Abacha's demise, he is still talked about in local and international media. Not for any good he did – he did none as a dictator! – but the evil he perpetrated. Worldwide, Abacha's name is a byword for utter brutality and grand corruption.

Adichie's literary searchlight on General Buhari's regime of the early eighties equally reflects hardship and high-handedness; oppression and suppression of the citizenry having stated that "General Buhari's soldiers were flogging adults in the streets, lecturers were striking for better pay..." (p.232),

on account of which Obinze's mother "...had decided that he could no longer have Fanta whenever he wanted but only on Sundays, with permission"(p.232). In historical reality, General Buhari's regime which lasted between 31st December, 1983 and 27th August, 1985 truly saw many citizens facing disheartening economic hardship as essential commodities were in very short supply. People queued up in long lines to be able to purchase rice, beans, tins of milk, etc from warehouses, shops and supermarkets in quantities highly regulated and regimented by military men and women who flogged citizens like animals. As in Abacha's regime, which came on board eight years after Buhari was overthrown by General Ibrahim Babangida, many citizens equally suffered certain unjustifiable incarcerations and torture during the Buhari era. Adichie sheds more light on the regime when she states:

IN DETENTION, he felt raw, skinned, the outer layers of himself stripped off. His mother's voice on the phone was almost unfamiliar, a woman speaking a crisp Nigerian English, telling him, calmly, to be strong, that she would be in Lagos to receive him, and he remembered how, years ago, when General Buhari's government stopped giving essential commodities, and she no longer came home with free tins of milk, she had begun to grind soya beans at home to make milk. She said soya milk was more nutritious than cow milk and although he refused to drink the grainy fluid in the morning, he watched her do so with an uncomplaining common sense. (*Americanah*, p.281)

This remembrance comes to Obinze at the Manchester Airport detention facility when he is about to be deported back to Nigeria, having traveled to the United Kingdom without proper documentation. Here again, General Buhari's regime is reminisced as the government which inflicts economic hardship on the citizenry. Now that Buhari has returned to power and is currently serving as Nigeria's civilian president, one wonders how and what will be remembered of him after now. On June 23, 2020, Godwin Tsa in his *Daily Sun* newspaper report captioned "Southern Leaders Slam N50bn Against Buhari, Malami Over Alleged Marginalisation" states that "A group of elder statesmen and leaders of socio-cultural platforms in Southern Nigeria have instituted a N50 billion suit against President Muhammadu Buhari at the Abuja division of the Federal High Court over alleged lopsided appointments of the administration." This is the same allegation that has trailed the administration from inception in 2015. Yet Buhari has about 2 years to determine how history could judge him in many years to come.

Earlier before his deportation, in a conversation between Obinze and Duerdinhito – a Brazilian, the significant Nigerian historical soccer victory in Atlanta 1996 Olympic games is alluded to when the narrator states: "They talked while emptying their vacuum cleaners, about the 1996 Olympics, Obinze gloating about Nigeria beating Brazil and then Argentina" (*Americanah*, p.251).

The narrator goes on to even mention one of the important figures behind Nigeria's soccer success in Atlanta 1996 Olympic games when Duerdinhito says, "Kanu was good, I give him that. But Nigeria had luck" (p.251). Kanu Nwankwo, of course, was Nigeria's Super Eagles Captain that led the team to that victorious feat in 1996. Adichie's reflection and allusion to Kanu and indeed the entire Super Eagles squad of that year for their noble effort in leading the nation to such a great feat is a deserved commendation in the hall of fame. That effort remains vivid and indelible in the hearts of many Nigerians till today; for which reason many of the participants in that historic soccer feat are still receiving various colourful garlands in one way or the other from both governmental and non-governmental organizations. This demonstrates that in-as-much as dictators and bad leaders are remembered and vilified for their bad governance and suppression of society, those whose honest commitment, dedication to duty and patriotism lead to elevation and addition of value to society are

equally remembered and given their due placements in the hall of fame. One therefore needs to make a choice while still on duty for history will surely remember and investigate. Unfortunately, those who are consigned to the dustbin of history do not often have the opportunity to re-write it or upturn its verdict.

Adichie's romance with history and historical developments in *Americanah* seemed to have come to a climax on a note of glamour with her allusion to a notable beauty icon when she states:

Ranyinudo had told her that his wife, when she was a student, was voted the most beautiful girl at the University of Lagos, and in Ifemelu's imagination, she looked like Bianca Onoh, that beauty icon of her teenage years, high-cheekboned and almond-eyed. (*Americanah*, p.412-413)

Bianca Onoh is a Nigerian who was a popular metaphor for beauty not only in Nigeria and Africa but the entire globe in the late 80s and even in the 90s, having won several prestigious beauty contests from the national level to the global platform. In commemoration of the 30th anniversary of those glorious feats which catapulted her to global prominence, Bianca on December 4, 2018 writes on her Facebook wall:

Thirty years ago this day, 4th Dec. 1988, I ventured in trepidation onto the grand stage of the National Theatre, Lagos, as a contestant in the MOST BEAUTIFUL GIRL IN NIGERIA PAGEANT by Silverbird Productions. By the grace of God I won the contest. I was then a law undergraduate at the University of Nigeria. The rest, as they say, is history.

Then it was the era of 'winner takes all' as pageant winner. From there I took off to Banjul, where the MISS AFRICA Pageant was held and I once again emerged the winner. Next was the MISS CHARM contest in MOSCOW which saw me emerge as Miss Drushbah. After that was the MISS INTERCONTINENTAL Pageant. I am the first African ever to have won this pageant. This was an awesome experience which provided a wonderful opportunity to visit over 20 countries of the world in the space of one year of 'reign' (a great privilege for a mere student) including 12 European countries as well as several other world destinations including Singapore, Japan, Russia, Taipei, Dubai, Republic of China, Hong Kong where I represented Nigeria at the Miss World beauty pageant and Cancun, Mexico where I was the country's representative at the MISS UNIVERSE Pageant. It is to God's glory that I went this far. Today, as always, I continue to celebrate the amazing opportunities God has thrown along my path in life. This is just one of them. (Bianca Ojukwu, 2018, *Fb*)

The beautiful climactic allusion to the character of this significant historic development in Adichie's *Americanah* suggests that the deployment of historical resources in an artistic creation does not just convey and deepen diverse meanings but also contributes to its aesthetic value. It ignites an artistic work, and helps to connect or reconnect a reader to certain important historical developments in society so that a reader can have an insightful and broader perception of issues that will enable him to better interpret the present and also make some meaningful prognosis. It is like Achebe's or rather Igbo maxim about knowing where the rain started beating one in order to know where it stops or will stop. The saying goes that one who does not remember where the rain started beating him will also not remember where it stops. This also implies that to understand and appropriately interpret the present, a concrete and realistic knowledge of the past is vital.

CONCLUSION

The study has basically examined the deployment of the novelistic art as a forensic and dialectic tool as exemplified in Chimamanda Adichie's *Americanah*. Adichie has realistically documented and interpreted historical developments in both her country of birth, Nigeria and other geographical domains which define the setting of the work, using diverse artistic techniques and in such manners considered relevant to her artistic enterprise and vision. She has clearly and consistently demonstrated in her novel under study that being a good novelist or writer goes beyond the ability to creatively manipulate lexico-semantic and syntactic resources but also that it involves a thorough and deep acquaintance with the historical developments of the society being written about since society, history and literature have always been harmonious, almost inseparable companions. The study of Adichie's *Americanah*, therefore, is to a reasonable extent a study of historical developments in Nigeria, and relatively a few of certain significant historical issues in some other places beyond Africa. The novel demonstrates profound and vivid allusions to a variety of notable national and global historical occurrences and can be said to be an excellent melting pot of historicity and artistry.

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